

Solvent effects on the kinetics of oxidation of methionine by nicotinium dichromate

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Abstract : The oxidation of methionine by nicotinium dichromate (NDC) has been studied, in the presence of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid, in water-DMSO and water-acetic acid mixtures of varying mole fractions. The reaction is first order each with respect to NDC and acid. The reaction rates have been determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters have been computed. The rate of decomposition of the complex increases with increase in mole fraction of acetic acid in the mixture while in water-DMSO mixtures the rate decreases with increasing mole fraction of the organic co-solvent. A possible mechanism for the reaction is postulated.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, methionine, solvent effect.

The kinetics of oxidation of organic compounds in non-aqueous and aquo-organic solvent mixtures have revealed the important role of non-specific and specific solvent effects on the reactivity¹. It has been shown that the reactivity is influenced by the preferential solvation of the reactants and/or transition state through non-specific and specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions. Furthermore, it has been established that the technique of correlation analysis may well be used to separate and quantify such solvent-solvent-solute interactions on reactivity.

Extensive studies on the mechanism of oxidation of methionine (Met) by several oxidants have been reported. This sulphur containing essential amino acid is reported to behave differently, in comparison to other amino acids, towards many oxidants². This may well be due to the presence of an electron-rich sulphur centre, which is easily oxidisable. Nicotinium dichromate (NDC) is reported to be a mild, stable and selective oxidant³. In this article, we report the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of methionine by NDC in water-DMSO and water-acetic acid mixtures of varying mole fractions, with a view to understand the utility of solvent variation studies in understanding the mechanism of this biologically important amino acid because it may reveal the mechanism of amino acid metabolism. Furthermore, solvent mixtures are very useful for studying solvent effects upon reactions since the properties of various mixed solvents can be adjusted continuously by changing the composition of the mixture.

Results and discussion

The reactions are first order with respect to NDC. Further, the values of k_{obs} are independent of the initial concentration of NDC (Table 1). The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions and the order with respect to $[\text{H}^+]$ is one. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of methionine (Table 2). The plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{Met}]^{-1}$ is linear with definite intercept on the rate ordinate and the values of equilibrium and rate constants calculated from the plots are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Pseudo-first-order rate constants for the oxidation of methionine by NDC in water at 25 ± 0.1 °C

10^2 [Met] (M)	10^3 [NDC] (M)	10 [Acid] (M)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
2.0	1.0	3.0	43.31
2.0	1.25	3.0	43.02
2.0	1.5	3.0	42.99
2.0	1.75	3.0	43.44
2.0	2.0	3.0	43.12
1.0	1.0	3.0	21.25
1.5	1.0	3.0	34.99
2.0	1.0	3.0	43.31
2.5	1.0	3.0	49.02
2.0	1.0	3.0	23.45 ^a
1.0	1.0	1.0	3.98
1.0	1.0	1.5	6.23
1.0	1.0	2.0	10.55
1.0	1.0	2.5	12.54

^aContained 5×10^{-4} M Mn^{II}.

The oxidation of Met in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the

rate of oxidation decreases with the addition of Mn^{II} indicating the involvement of a two electron reduction of Cr^{VI} to Cr^{IV} . Therefore, a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals is unlikely. The rate of oxidation of Met was determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated and are listed in Table 3.

Table 2. Effect of organic co-solvent on the rate of oxidation of methionine by NDC at 25 ± 0.1 °C

[Met] = 2×10^{-2} M; [NDC] = 1×10^{-3} M						
Co-solvent	10^2 [Met], M				K	$10^3 k$
m.f.	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.75		
Water-acetic acid mixtures ^a						
0	0.025	0.030	0.035	0.037	32.9	0.01
0.1	1.67	2.10	2.25	2.69	18.3	1.09
0.2	2.94	3.41	4.04	5.19	19.4	1.84
0.3	4.99	5.66	7.21	7.43	20.2	2.91
0.4	5.71	7.67	8.20	9.18	13.3	5.03
0.5	13.85	15.94	18.18	22.14	20.7	8.07
0.6	19.61	22.97	25.02	33.18	15.6	14.29
0.7	30.79	37.79	46.15	52.09	11.9	26.24
Water-DMSO mixtures ^b						
0	21.25	34.99	43.31	49.02	1.7	1273
0.1	16.95	25.77	27.23	42.75	8.6	214
0.2	11.54	17.31	20.75	21.85	21	69
0.3	4.31	5.23	5.41	6.34	104	8.45
0.4	3.10	3.16	4.28	1.38	100	5.98
0.5	2.43	2.74	3.60	3.22	103	4.76
0.6	1.98	2.15	2.49	2.84	113	3.63
0.7	1.73	1.95	2.13	2.48	116	3.17

^aIn presence of [TsOH] = 0.075 M; ^bin presence of [TsOH] = 0.3 M.

Mechanism : Under the experimental conditions employed in the present study methionine is oxidized to the corresponding sulphoxide stage only. Based on the above kinetic observations the following mechanism has been proposed for the reaction. The linear increase in rate with acidity suggests the involvement of protonated NDC in the rate-determining step. In the first step NDC gets protonated. The protonated NDC attacks the substrate to form a complex, in a pre-equilibrium step, and which subsequently decomposes to give the products in a slow step. The proposed scheme envisages an oxygen atom transfer from the oxidant and that is in agreement with earlier observations involving the oxidation of sulphur containing compounds with halochromates. The electrophilic attack on the sulphide-sulphur can be viewed as an S_N2 reaction. An S_N2 like transition state (more hydrophobic) is supported by the observed solvent effect.

The above mechanism leads to the following rate law :

$$-d[NDC]/dt = KK'k [Met] [NDC] [H^+]$$

The influence of solvent on the rate of the reaction was studied in water-organic solvent mixtures at different mole fractions of organic co-solvent viz. acetic acid (protic, hydrogen bond donor) and DMSO (aprotic, non-hydrogen bond donor). The results in Table 2 indicate that the rate constants for the decomposition of complex (k) are remarkably sensitive to the nature and the composition of the mixed solvent. The rate constants increase with increasing mole fraction of acetic acid and decrease with increasing mole fraction of DMSO in the mixture.

Table 3. Effect of temperature and thermodynamic parameters for the oxidation of methionine by NDC in water at [TsOH] = 0.05 M and [NDC] = 0.001 M

Temp. (K)	10^4 [Met], M				K	$10^3 k$	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
	1.00	1.50	2.00	2.50					
298	4.17	5.88	7.60	7.84	22	2.32			
303	5.01	6.43	8.86	10.27	17	3.36	73.38	-49.60	88.16
308	5.60	7.98	10.02	12.67	10	6.29			

ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol⁻¹; ΔS^\ddagger J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹; ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol⁻¹.

A plot of log k versus inverse of relative permittivity of the medium, through Laidler-Eyring⁴ equation, is non-linear in both the aquo-organic solvent media (in water-acetic acid mixtures : $r = 0.759$, $sd = 0.74$ and in water-DMSO mixtures : $r = 0.875$, $sd = 0.51$). Hence, the effect of solvent on reactivity may be understood from the standpoint of specific solvation effect and non-specific solvation effect⁵. The rate data were correlated with the Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters with following Linear Solvation Energy Relationship (LSER)⁶.

$$\log k = A_0 + s\pi^* + a\alpha + b\beta$$

where π^* is an index of solvent dipolarity/polarizability, which measures the ability of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect, α is the solvent HBD (hydrogen bond donor) acidity, β is the solvent HBA (hydrogen bond acceptor) basicity of the solvent in a solute to solvent hydrogen bond and A_0 is the regression value of the solute property in the reference solvent cyclohexane. The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property log k to the indicated solvent parameter. The rate of oxidation in both the solvent mixtures studied show excellent correlations with solvent via the above LSER. The correlation results obtained are given under.

In water-acetic acid mixtures :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \log k &= -33.99 - 6.08 \pi^* + 18.21 \alpha + 43.31 \beta \\
 (N &= 8, R^2 = 0.992, sd = 0.13, P_\alpha = 27\%, P_\beta = 64\%, \\
 &P_{\pi^*} = 9\%)
 \end{aligned}$$

In water-DMSO mixtures :

$$\log k = -12.39 + 2.87 \pi^* + 4.18 \alpha + 7.38 \beta$$

($N = 8$, $R^2 = 0.987$, $sd = 0.15$, $P_\alpha = 29\%$, $P_\beta = 51\%$,
 $P_{\pi^*} = 20\%$)

Such an excellent correlation, with an explained variance of *ca.* 99% in both the aquo-organic solvent mixtures, indicates the existence of both non-specific and specific solute-solvent-solvent interactions. From the values of the regression coefficients the contribution of each parameter (P_x), on a percentage basis, to reactivity were calculated¹. The results of the Kamlet-Taft correlation indicate that the contribution of specific solute-solvent interactions, as explained by the α and β terms, was found to be predominant and positive sign of the coefficients of these terms in both the water-organic solvent mixtures indicate that the specific interactions between the transition state and the solvent mixture is more than that between the reactants and solvent mixture.

Blandamer and Burgess⁷ have classified aqueous mixtures on the basis of their thermodynamic properties, particularly their molar excess functions, X^E . Water-acetic acid is classified as typically non-aqueous positive (TNAP) mixture (G^E is positive) and water-DMSO as typically non-aqueous negative (TNAN) mixture for which G^E is negative. Further, an extra-thermodynamic analysis indicates that, at least qualitatively, if G^E is positive the solute should be more soluble in the mixture than predicted from the solubilities in the two pure solvents.

In the present study, in water-acetic acid mixtures the rate of the oxidation increases with increase in mole fraction of the co-solvent while in water-DMSO mixtures the rate decreases with increase in mole fraction of the co-solvent. In other words in a TNAP mixture the rate increases as G^E increases and in a TNAN mixture the rate decreases as G^E decreases. This may be due to the fact that the transition state is more hydrophobic than the initial state, so that such a transition state is stabilized in a TNAP solvent mixture; consequently the rate increases with increase in mole fraction of acetic acid in the mixture. However, in water-DMSO mixtures, the transition state is not stabilized to such an extent hence the rate of the reaction decreases.

In conclusion, the reaction is highly influenced by the amount and nature of the organic co-solvent added to the mixture. Linear and multiple regression analysis may be used to separate and quantify the specific and non-specific solvational effects on the oxidation of methionine by NDC.

Using the above method the significance of those solvent-solvent-solute interactions on the reactivity has been established. From the regression coefficients information on the solvent-reactant and the solvent-transition state interactions is obtained.

Experimental

Methionine (Merck) was used as supplied. NDC was prepared by the reported method³ and its purity was checked by iodometric assay. *p*-Toluene sulphonic acid was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Solvents were purified by the standard methods.

Kinetic measurements : The reaction was studied under pseudo-first-order conditions by keeping an excess of the substrate over the oxidant. The solvent was pure water unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were studied at constant temperature (± 0.1 °C) in the presence of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (0.3 M) and were followed up to 80% completion by monitoring the decrease in [NDC] iodometrically. Pseudo-first-order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear plots of ($r^2 > 0.97$) \log [NDC] against time. Replicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants are reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by performing the experiment under the conditions of [NDC] > [Met]. The disappearance of NDC was monitored until constant titre values were obtained. The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. The oxidation of Met resulted in the formation of the corresponding sulphoxide. The sulphoxide was determined by the reported method⁸. The yield of the sulphoxide was $87 \pm 5\%$.

Data analysis : Correlation analyses were carried out using Microcal Origin (version 6) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using correlation coefficient, r , in the case of simple regression and R in the case of multiple regression analysis and standard deviation, sd .

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